

PERFECT POWERS IN THE SMARANDACHE PERMUTATION SEQUENCE

Maohua Le

Department of Mathematics, Zhanjiang Normal College
Zhanjiang, Guangdong, P.R.China.

Abstract. In this paper we prove that the Smarandache permutation sequence does not contain perfect powers.

Let $S = \{S_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be the Smarandache permutation sequence. Then we have

$$(1) \quad s_1 = 12, \quad s_2 = 1342, \quad s_3 = 135642, \quad s_4 = 13578642, \dots$$

In [1, Notion 6], Dumitrescu and Seleacu posed the following question:

Question . Is there any perfect power belonging to S ?

In this respect, Smarandache [2] conjectured: no! In this paper we verify the above conjecture as follows:

Theorem. The sequence S does not contain powers.

Proof. Let s_n be a perfect power. Since $2 \mid s_n$ by (1), then we have

$$(2) \quad 4 \mid s_n.$$

Since $s_1 = 12$ is not a perfect power, we get $n > 1$. Then

from (1) we get

$$(3) \quad s_n = 10^2 a + 42,$$

where a is a positive integer. Notice that $4 \mid 10^2$ and $4 \nmid 42$. We find from (3) that $4 \nmid s_n$, which contradicts (2). Thus, the theorem is proved.

References

1. Dumitrescu and Seleacu, Some Notions and Questions In Number Theory, Erhus Univ. Press, Glendale, 1994.
2. F.Smarandache, Only Problems, not Solutions! Xiquan Pub. House, Phoenix, Chicago, 1990.